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A GREEN CURE FOR ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE: A CRITICAL REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a progressive brain disease that affects a person's memory, learning ability, intellectual, judgment, communication, and daily activities over time. Clinically, Alzheimer's disease is marked by cognitive impairment, while pathologically, it is marked by the formation of amyloid plaques and neurofibrillary tangles, as well as the degradation of the cholinergic basal forebrain. The primary neurotransmitter defect discovered in AD involved acetylcholine as cholinergic function is vital for temporary memory. Although the Food and Drug Administration has official numerous medicines for the handling of Alzheimer's disease, the results have not been satisfactory, and alternative medicine, including herbal therapy, has a role. Herbal remedies for Alzheimer's disease have become more and more popular in the recent years, some herbs that is Saga, Gotu Kala, Jyotishmati, Brahmi, Shankhpusph, Lavender, Chinese date and Saffron are useful for cognitive impairment of Alzheimer's disease. Most of the plants have been chemically evaluated with their proven efficacy in clinical trials. Current review summarizes data concerning the sources, chemistry, biological actions and clinical applications of these plants to give adequate baseline facts that could be used in drug discovery & development process, thereby providing new functional molecules for Alzheimer's disease.

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INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a liberal and irretrievable neurological illness that occurs steadily and outcomes in memory damage, uncommon behavior, behavior changes, and loss of the skill to thinking. [1] AD starts with loss of short-term memory, forgetting names and addresses, as this illness advances, the change become more notice able and even personalities forget the home way. Improperly, AD has not any remedy but can be barred from continuing. Seventy percent of causes for AD is hereditary and 21% is eco-friendly. Most cases of Alzheimer's, about 95%, are the late-onset form, which progresses after age 60. [2] Brain areas associated with cognitive functions, particularly the neocortex and hippocampus, are the areas that frequently pretentious by the pathology which is representative of AD. [3] Better understanding of the disease process and designed clinical trial are step forward and have improved related treatments for cognitive and non-cognitive symptoms. Pharmacological treatment strategies in AD include three categories of drug: 1) their mechanism is based on disease-modifying therapies such as vitamin E; 2) their mechanism is based on compensation of neurotransmitter such as a cholinesterase inhibitor; 3) psychotherapy factors that are prescribed for symptoms of conduct disorder. [4] Medicinal plants that have shown the early promising signs of clinical efficacy in the treatment of AD have been reviewed. One mutual feature of these plants is their capability to exert neuroprotective properties through inhibition of AChE or inhibition of oxidative stress. Although recently several synthetic drugs have been introduced to treat learning and memory disorder, but their therapeutic effects are low and most of them have undesirable side effects. [5] Current review offers the description of medicinal plants that possesses promising role in Alzheimer.

Disease Profile

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a progressive and irreversible loss of cognitive function caused by senile plaques in the hippocampus region of the brain. [6] It is a neurological ailment that progresses over time and is a leading cause of dementia in the elderly. The major symptoms of this disease in the elderly are difficulty with home routines and cognitive and emotional disturbances. It has an impact on memory, cognition, and behavior. [7] So far, efforts to develop a cure for Alzheimer's disease have been unsuccessful, and the medications now available to treat the condition merely address its symptoms and are ineffective. A loss of neurons in the hippocampus, cortex, and subcortical regions is the underlying an etiology. [8]

Figure 1. Neurological Damage Leads to the Decrease of Cortical & Hippocamal Size (Adopted from Agarwal P. et.al.2013).

There are 2 classes of Alzheimer's disease:

Early onset AD:

Indications begin to arise before the age of 60. This is a considerably rarer condition than late onset. It does, however, tend to deteriorate swiftly. Early-onset sickness can be passed down through peers. A number of genetic factors have been visible.

Late onset AD:

This is the most typical. It disturbs persons over the age of 60. Although it appears to run in certain families, the function of genes is unclear. [9]

Causes

Age-related changes in the brain:

One of the countless ambiguities of Alzheimer's disease is why it mainly attacks grown-ups. Research on how the brain changes normally with age is shedding light on this question. For instance, researchers are learning how growth-related changes in the brain may damage neurons and contribute to Alzheimer's impairment.

Genetics:

Alzheimer's disease with onset at a young age is an uncommon occurrence. It affects persons between the ages of 30 and 60 and accounts for fewer than 5% of all Alzheimer's patients. The common cases of early-onset Alzheimer's are triggered by mutations in one of three identified genes inherited from a parent. The most entities with Alzheimer's ailment have late-onset, which stereotypically produces after age, 60. Numerous studies have allied the APOE gene to late-onset Alzheimer's. This gene has numerous forms. One of them, APOE ϵ 4, seems to upsurge an individual's risk of receiving the sickness. Though, booming the APOE ϵ 4 form of the inheritable factor does not necessarily mean that an individual will develop Alzheimer's disease, and persons carrying no APOE ϵ 4 can also grow the disease.

Environmental/lifestyle factors:

A variety of variables other than fundamental genetics may potentially have a role in the development and progression of Alzheimer's disease, according to research. Associations between cognitive decline and vascular and metabolic disorders such as heart disease, stroke, high blood pressure, diabetes, and obesity, for example, are of significant interest. Understanding these connections and putting them to the test in clinical trials will help us figure out if lowering risk factors for these disorders can also assist with Alzheimer's. [10]

Plaques:

The sec lumps of beta amyloid protein may harm and kill brain cells in a variety of ways, including interfering with cell-to-cell communication. Although the exact origin of Alzheimer's disease brain cell loss is unknown, the accumulation of beta-amyloid on the exterior of brain cells is a leading possibility.

Tangles:

Brain cells hinge on an internal care and passage system to transfer nutrients and other essential materials throughout their long extensions. This arrangement requires the standard structure and functioning of a protein called tau. In Alzheimer's, cobwebs of tau protein twist into atypical tangles inside brain cells, leading to disaster of the passage system. This letdown is also strongly concerned in the weakening and death of brain cells. [11]

Pathogenesis:

Scopolamine may chemically induce experimental animals to have impaired learning and memory, which is the most common sign of dementia. Scopolamine is a recognized cholinergic antagonist that involved in the spread of acetylcholine in the central nervous system. [12] Cholinergic transmission is mainly terminated by acetylcholine hydrolysis by the enzyme AChE, which is in charge for deprivation of acetylcholine to acetate and choline in the synaptic cleft. [13] Scopolamine-induced forgetfulness in animal replicas is widely used to screen for mixtures with potential therapeutic value in treatment of dementia. [14] Decrease of acetylcholine transferase enzyme activity and loss of cholinergic neurons were observed in the basal portion of the frontal brain of AD patient that connected with cognitive diminishing. [15] The nucleus basalis of Meynert (NBM) lesion patterns are used to investigate the function of the cortical cholinergic system in consciousness and understanding, as well as to identify cognitive abnormalities induced by Alzheimer's disease. [16] Cholinergic indicators such as acetylcholine levels, acetylcholine release and turnover, acetylcholine uptake, AChE activity, and the number of cholinergic muscarinic receptors in the frontal cortex were all reduced when NBM was destroyed in animal models. [17] Electrical damage of NBM causes death of cholinergic cells in this nucleus and lowers the quantity of acetylcholine in the cortex because cholinergic ramifications are delivered from Meynert nuclei into the cortex and septal region. [18] Hippocampus plays a critical role in learning and memory, which is a complex biological process including the acquisition, consolidation and retrieval of information. [19] Neurogenesis in the hippocampus, defined as the generation of new nerve cells, is involved in memory formation. Amplified neurogenesis has enhanced spatial remembrance while diminished neurogenesis specifies poor cognitive role. [20] Deposition of amyloid plaques in brain tissue and meningeal blood vessels, as well as the presence of neurofibrillary tangles in the hippocampus and cerebral cortex, are important neuro pathological characteristics of Alzheimer's disease. [21] Recent studies have demonstrated that AD is associated with inflammatory processes. Reactive oxidative types can harm cellular components and function as a second messenger in the tenderness. Consumption of antioxidants may be beneficial in anticipation and treatment of AD. [22] Oxidative stress, which is defined as an imbalance between free radicals and antioxidant systems, is solitary element that plays a crucial part in the etiology of Alzheimer's disease. Free radicals in the presence of oxygen can destroy proteins, nucleic acids, and lipid membranes, disrupting cellular function and integrity. Polyunsaturated fatty acids, which are abundant in brain tissue, are particularly sensitive to free radical damage. Both the loop and splitting forms of oxygenated fatty acids have neurotoxic effects, and lipid peroxidation is assumed to be a harmful kind of oxidative breakdown that damages cell membranes and creates a number of secondary metabolites. [23] Increase in the levels of malondialdehyde (MDA), one of the reactive oxidative species, has been recognized as an important lipid peroxidation indicator. [24]

Various plants are the subject of extensive investigation across the world. Plant extracts are more therapeutically beneficial, have less adverse effects, and are less expensive. Plant extracts might be a source of novel chemicals, including a number of medications generated from plants.

Synthetic Drug Treatment:

Synthetic drugs for AD include donepezil, rivastigmine, galantamine and memantine. For controlling aggressive, angry, or risky behaviors, additional medications like haloperidol, risperidone, and quetiapine are used. Due to the potential of adverse effects, such as an increased chance of mortality, they are normally administered in extremely low dosages. [25]

TABLE 1: SYNTHETIC DRUGS USED IN ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE.

	Drugs	Mode of Action	Uses	Side- effects
1	Memantine	It acts as a non-competitive antagonist at different neuronal nicotinic receptors (nAChRs) at potencies similar to the NMDA and 5-HT ₃ receptors. [26]	It is used for managing people with moderate to severe AD's who are possibly intolerant to cholinesterase inhibitors. [27]	Headache, Confusion, Sleepiness, Abnormal liver function, Balance disorder, Breathlessness, Hypertension.
2	Donepezil	It is a reversible inhibitor of the enzyme acetylcholinesterase. Acetylcholinesterase is an enzyme, which breaks down the Neurotransmitter acetylcholine. [28]	It is used to treat confusion (dementia) related to Alzheimer's disease. [29]	Nausea, Vomiting, Diarrhea.
3	Cimetidine	It binds to an H ₂ -receptor located on the basal lateral membrane of the gastric parietal cell, blocking histamine effects. [30]	It is effective in the treatment of common warts, herpes zoster, calcific tendinitis and Alzheimer's Disease. [31]	Headache, Diarrhea, Muscle pain, Tiredness
4	Rivastigmine	It binds reversibly with and inactivates cholinesterase, preventing the hydrolysis of acetylcholine, and thus leading to an increased concentration of acetylcholine at synapses. [32]	It is used to treat dementia related to Alzheimer's disease. It may improve memory, awareness, and the ability to perform daily functions. [33]	Nausea, Vomiting, Indigestion.
5	Haloperidol	It is a typical butyrophenone type antipsychotic that exhibits high affinity dopamine D ₂ receptor antagonism and slow receptor kinetics. [34]	It has found it to be an effective agent in treatment of schizophrenia, Alzheimer's disease, sclerosis, delirium. [35]	Abnormal voluntary movements, Constipation, Dryness in mouth, Orthostatic hypotension, Tremor, Urinary retention.
6	Risperidone	Blockade of dopaminergic D ₂ receptors in the limbic system alleviates positive symptoms of Schizophrenia such as hallucinations, delusions, and erratic behavior and speech. [36]	It is used in people with dementia, such as those suffering from Alzheimer's disease. [37]	Headache, Insomnia, Parkinsonism, Drowsiness, Sedation.
7	Galantamine	It reduces the action of AChE and therefore tends to increase the concentration of acetylcholine in the brain. [38]	It is used for indicated for the treatment of mild to moderate and Alzheimer's. [39]	Headache, Vomiting, Diarrhea, Dizziness, Decreased appetite, Weight loss.

Herbal Drugs used in Alzheimer's Disease:***Salvia officinalis*:**

- **Common Name:** Sage
- **Parts used:** Flowers, leaves and stem
- **Family:** Lamiaceae

• **Chemical Constituents:** It includes essential oils, naphthodianthrones, phloroglucinols, and flavonoids (such as phenylpropanes, flavanol glycosides, and biflavones). Hypericin and hyperforin are the two main active ingredients. [40]

Pharmacology and Mode of Action:

In mice, *H. Perforatum* protects them against Parkinson's disease caused by MPTP. [41] In the striatal region of (MPTP) provoked mice, *H. Perforatum* extract inhibited MAOB (monoamine oxidase B) activity and lowered astrocyte activation. The flavanols quercetin and kaempferol are neuroprotective because they reduce lipid membrane oxidation and sustain mitochondrial transmembrane electric potential & reduce mitochondrial calcium absorption capacity. [42] Hypericin may interfere with the polymerization processes of the beta-amyloid peptide that causes Alzheimer's disease. [43]

Rosmarinus officinalis:

- **Common Name:** Rosemary
- **Parts used:** Flowers and leaves
- **Family:** Lamiaceae
- **Chemical Constituents:** It contains carnosic acid, rosmarinic acid, camphor, caffeic acid, ursolic acid, betulinic acid, rosmaridiphenol androsmanol. [44]

Pharmacology and Mode of Action:

Rosmarinus officinalis has been shown to have considerable neuroprotective properties in the treatment of neurodegenerative illnesses including Alzheimer's and dementia. Acetylcholine-Cholinesterase (AChE) and Butyryl Cholinesterase (BChE) are two enzymes in the brain that break down acetylcholine. Rosemary has inhibitory properties against both of these enzymes (BChE). Rosmarinic acid and terpene chemicals in the plant's essential oil are thought to be the cause of these anti-AChE and anti-BChE actions. [45] Rosemary may help to prevent Alzheimer's disease, as well as memory loss, anxiety, and depression, by raising total choline levels in the brain. [46] Rosemary extract polyphenols were rediscovered to block stress proteins, which are involved in the neurodegenerative process. [47] Rosemary increases the synthesis of Nerve Development Factor (NGF), a protein important for nerve tissue growth and maintenance. NGF levels that are higher can aid in the treatment of Alzheimer's disease, dementia, and other neurodegenerative illnesses. [48]

Centella asiatica:

- **Common Name:** Gotu Kola, Mandukpuri
- **Parts used:** Leaves
- **Family:** Umbelliferae.
- **Chemical Constitution:** It contains asiatic acid and asiaticoside. [49]

Pharmacology and Mode of Action:

Neuroprotection aspect of this is mainly involves enzyme inhibition, prevention of amyloid plaque formation in AD'S, dopamine neurotoxicity in PD'S, and lowering oxidative stress. [50] In primary cultures of rat cortical neurons, the activity of subtypes of phospholipase A2 (PLA2) was assessed, and asiaticoside included in the extract decreased cPLA2 and PLA2 activities. [51] Acute treatments of asiatic acid to male Sprague-Dawley rats resulted in better learning and memory. [52] Neuroprotective potential of modern medicine constituents of the plant includes asiatic acid, madecassic acid, and brahmaside as well as flavonoids madecassoside and madesiatic acid. [53] In aluminum-treated rats, *C. asiatica* was studied for its neuroprotective effects on cell death and cognitive irregularity. Chronic treatment of CA resulted in significant improvements in memory performance and oxidative defense. [54] The plant is known to utilize neuroprotective effects by attenuating the changes in an animal model such as pathological neurobehavioral and neurochemical properties. Phosphoinositides-assisted cytodynamics and synaptic function show the neuroprotective effects of asiaticoside in the rat which includes mode of ROT-infused hemi-parkinsonism. [55]

Celastrus Paniculatus:

- **Common Name:** Jyotishmati
- **Parts used:** Seed, fruit & leaves.
- **Family:** Celastraceae
- **Chemical Constitution:** Triacylglycerol (TAG), free fatty acids (FFA), diacylglycerol (DAG), esterified sterols (STE) and monoacylglycerol (MAG) are all present. [56]

Pharmacology and Mode of Action:

A research found that continuous oral treatment of *Celastrus Paniculatus* seed oil corrected the spatial memory declension caused by central musurinic receptor blockage in rats. [57] Bhagya et al., 2016 investigated the same effect in Wistar rats with *Celastrus Paniculatus* oil.[58]They observed rats in the open field and subsequently conducted behavioral tests in a darkened room. Anxiety tests were then conducted using raised plus maze, partly baited radial arm maze, and T-maze rewarded altering task techniques. According to their findings, a chronic dosage of *Celastrus Paniculatus* seed oil has neuroprotective properties against chronic stress-induced cognitive impairment. [59]

Bacopa monnieri:

Common Name: Brahmi

- **Parts used:** Leaves and stem.
- **Family:** Scrophulariaceae
- **Chemical Constitution:** Bacoside A, Bacoside, Betulinic acid, D-Mannitol, Stigmastanol, b-Sitosterol, Stigmasterol. [60]

Pharmacology and Mode of Action:

It has shown to diminish beta-amyloid deposits in the cortex and correct behavioral impairments in rats.[61]The impact of an alcoholic extract of *B. monnieri* on an animal model of Alzheimer's disease produced by ethylcholine aziridinium ion was investigated, and it was discovered that the extract enhanced the escape latency time in the Morris' water maze test. The loss of neurons and the density of cholinergic neurons were similarly reduced. [62]There was an improvement in cognitive skills of Alzheimer's disease patients when 300mg of standardized extract of *B. monnieri* was given orally two times a day for six months. [63] Methanol extract of *B.monniieri* (leaves and stem) was shown to have acetylcholinesterase inhibitory properties in research. [64] Another research found that *B.monniieri* contains an endogenous chemical that affects components of the oxidative stress cascade, such as divalent metal reduction, reactive oxygen species scavenging, and lipoxygenase activity. Polyphenols and sulphhydryl content are found in *B. monnieri* extract. [65]According to Tembhe, *B. monnieri* inhibited acetylcholinesterase in the rat cerebral cortex, and a kinetic analysis revealed that acetylcholinesterase inhibition was competitive in the brain areas. [66]

Convolvulus Pluricaulcis:

- **Common Name:** Shankhpushp
- **Parts used:** Whole plant issue.
- **Family:** Convolvulaceae
- **Chemical Constitution:** Convoline, convolidine, convolvine, confoline, convosine, kampferol and steroids phytosterol. [67]

Pharmacology and Mode of Action:

Due to its chemical makeup, it is one of the greatest and most well-known natural remedies for boosting memory. It's mostly employed as a brain tonic and stimulant. This should be consumed on a daily basis to avoid memory loss. The memory-enhancing characteristics of the ethanolic extract of CP, as well as ethyl acetate and aqueous fractions, were investigated. In response to plant treatment, Acetylcholine esterase activity in the CA1 and CA3 area of the hippocampus, which are implicated in learning and memory processes, increased dose-dependently. [68]

Lavandula officinalis:

- **Common Name:** English Lavender
- **Parts used:** Flowers.
- **Family:** Lamiaceae
- **Chemical Constitution:** Geraniol, linalool, linalyl acetate, cineol, borneol, aflapin, camphor, butyric acid, valerianic acid, ursolic acid, and luteolin flavonoids. [69]

Pharmacology and Mode of Action:

In rats subjected to ischemia and reperfusion, treatment with lavender essential oil dramatically reduced neurologic impairment, stroke volume, MDA, carbonyl, and reactive oxygen species levels, indicating a strong neuroprotective effect. [70] The increased activity of the AChE enzyme, which results in a lower quantity of acetylcholine and synaptic transmission, has been shown to contribute to the loss of spatial memory and the development of Alzheimer's disease. Various investigations on cell lines have demonstrated that varying concentrations of lavender extract inhibit the AChE enzyme. [71] Free radicals have been linked to phospholipid peroxidation, DNA damage, and protein denaturation. The hippocampus is an important part of the brain for spatial memory and learning. One of the most fundamental cellular processes underlying learning and memory is long-term potentiation. Increased antioxidant consumption enhances spatial learning and long-term potentiation induction in mice with Alzheimer's disease. [72]

Ziziphus jujube:

- **Common Name:** Chinese Date
- **Parts used:** Fruits
- **Family:** Rhamnaceae
- **Chemical Constitution:** The jujube fruit has yielded terpenoid, flavonoid, and alkaloid chemicals, as well as a phenyl glycosides substance. [73]

flavonols

flavones

flavanones

isoflavones

Pharmacology and Mode of Action:

Increased acetylcholine levels in cholinergic terminals might help to alleviate Alzheimer's symptoms and motor deficits. [74] Compensation of normal acetylcholine concentration in the synaptic cleft to promote neuronal transmission in the brain cholinergic terminals is one therapy option for Alzheimer's disease. Acetylcholine transferase activators raise acetylcholine levels to help people with mild to severe Alzheimer's disease improve their cognitive performance. [75] Learning and memory, motor coordination, and behavioral abnormalities induced by the Meynert nucleus lesion at the base of the rat brain's frontal lobe can be improved by jujube extract. This impact might be attributed to jujube extract's influence on acetylcholine transferase activity. It has the potential to lower the expensive cost of treating Alzheimer's disease, and it might be a good complement to synthetic and chemical medications that have a lot of side effects. [76]

Crocus sativus:

- **Common Name:** Saffron
- **Parts used:** Dried Stigma
- **Family:** Iridaceae
- **Chemical Constitution:** It contains Gentisic, gallic acids, lycopene, picrocrocin, safranal, crocin, zeaxanthin, α - and β -carotenes. [77]

Pharmacology and Mode of Action:

Saffron extract affected learning and memory in experimental animals, according to current behavioral and electrophysiological research. In mice, saffron extract corrected ethanol-induced learning deficits and reversed ethanol-induced suppression of hippocampus long-term potentiation, a kind of activity-dependent synaptic plasticity that underpins learning and memory. As a result, saffron extract or its active ingredients, crocetin and crocin, might be used to treat neurodegenerative illness associated with memory loss. The major therapy approach for Alzheimer's disease was inhibitors of acetylcholine breakdown by acetylcholinesterase (AChE). In vitro enzymatic and molecular docking investigations were used to investigate the suppression of AChE activity by saffron extract and its components. [78] The AChE inhibitory activity of saffron extract was modest (up to 30%), whereas the IC₅₀ values of crocetin, dimethyl crocetin, and safranal were 96.33, 107.1, and 21.09M, respectively. Mixed-type inhibition was discovered by kinetic analysis, which was confirmed by in silico docking experiments. Safranal exclusively binds to the AChE binding site, whereas crocetin and dimethylcrocetin bind to the catalytic and peripheral anionic sites together. [79]

Cyperus rotundus

- **Common Name:** Coco grass
- **Parts used:** Dried rhizomes
- **Family:** Cyperaceae

• **Chemical Constitution:** Pinene, a minor quantity of cineole, terpenes, and isociprol are all found in *Cyperus* rhizome essential oils. Several chemical components of the ethanol extract of *C. rotundus* rhizome have been discovered, and some of these chemicals exhibit anti-AChE properties. [80]

Pharmacology and Mode of Action:

The severity of dementia in Alzheimer's disease is linked to a loss in neurons in the Meynert nucleus, which is accompanied by a considerable drop in the number of acetylcholine transferase enzymes in the cortex and amygdala, resulting in poor learning. [81] The bulk of the cells in the NBM, which is located in the frontal base of the brain, are cholinergic. [82] Electrical injuries of NBM induces cholinergic cell death in the nucleus and lowers the quantity of acetylcholine in the cortex because cholinergic ramifications are delivered from Meynert nucleus to the cortex and septum.[83] Rats with damaged NBM were given two dosages of *C. rotundus* extracts in research. The anti-AChE action of *C. rotundus* extracts increased spatial learning, memory, and passive avoidance learning. [84]

TABLE 2: HERBAL DRUGS USED IN ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE:

Sr. No	Herbal Drug	Family	Active Chemical Constituents	Mode of Action
1	<i>Salvia officinalis</i> (Flowers, leaves and stem)	Lamiaceae	Naphthodianthrones, phloroglucionals	It is a neuroprotective agent against MPTP (1- methyle-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6 tetrahydropyridine) induced Parkinson's disease in mice. Its extract led to the inhibition of MAOB (monoamine oxidase B) activity and decreased astrocyte activation in striatal area of (MPTP).
2	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i> (Flower and leaves)	Lamiaceae	Carnosic Acid, Rosmarinic Acid, Rosmanol, Rosmaridiphenol	It showed inhibitory activities against the two enzymes in the brain responsible for the breakdown of AChE and BChE. By increasing total choline levels in the brain, rosemary could attenuate not just Alzheimer's disease, but also memory loss, anxiety and depression.
3	<i>Centella asiatica</i> (Leaves)	Umbelliferae	Asiatic Acid, Asiaticoside	It mainly involves Enzyme inhibition, prevention of amyloid Plaque formation in Alzheimer's disease, dopamine neurotoxicity in Parkinson's disease and reducing oxidative stress.
4	<i>Celastrus paniculatus</i> (Seed, fruit, leaves)	Celastraceae	Triacylglycerol, Free fatty acid, Diacylglycerol, Monoacylglycerol	It exhibits neuroprotective effects on chronic stress induced cognitive impairment.
5	<i>Bacopa monniera</i> (Leaves and stem)	Scrophulariaceae	Bacoside A, D-Mannitol, Stigmastanol	It reduces the beta- amyloid deposits in cortex and reversed behavioral deficits in brain. It has acetylcholinesterase inhibitory property.
6	<i>Convolvulus pluricaulics</i> (Whole plant)	Convolvulaceae	Convolvidine, Convoline, Kampferol	Hippocampal regions associated with the learning and memory functions showed a dose-dependent increase in acetylcholine esterase activity in the CA1 and CA3 area with plant treatment.
7	<i>Lavandula officinalis</i> (Flowers)	Lamiaceae	Geraniol, Linalool, Linalyl acetate, Valerianic acid	It decreased neurologic deficit, stroke volume, the level of MDA, carbonyl and showed strong neuroprotective effect.
8	<i>Ziziphus jujuba</i> (Fruits)	Rhamnaceae	Terpenoid, Flavonoids, Alkaloid compounds	Acetylcholine transferase activator increase acetylcholine level in order to improve mild to moderate cognitive function of AD.
9	<i>Crocus sativus</i> (Dried Stigma)	Iridaceae	Gentisic, Gallic Acids, Lycopene	It has improved ethanol- induced impairments of learning behaviors and prevented ethanol- induced inhibition of hippocampal long-term potentiation, a form of activity-dependent synaptic plasticity that may underlay learning & memory.
10	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> (Dried rhizomes)	Cyperaceae	Cineole, Terpenes	It has improved spatial learning and memory as well as passive avoidance learning.

CONCLUSION

In general, there is strong evidence that the ACh plays a role in Alzheimer's disease. Because cholinergic function is required for short-term memory, it was thought that cholinergic insufficiency in AD was to blame for much of the short-term memory loss. Because the etiology of AD is a complicated process including both hereditary and environmental variables, herbal remedies are recognized as novel and promising sources of prospective anti-AD therapies. Herbal therapies have the potential to cure Alzheimer's disease because of their cognitive advantages and, more importantly, their methods of action in relation to the illness's core pathophysiology. Several herbal remedies with possible therapeutic benefits for Alzheimer's disease have been identified in our review with no major side effects. Still clinical trials including larger sample sizes are still required to investigate the effects of different medicinal plants and the underlying mechanisms.

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Conflict of Interest:

The authors have no conflict of interests to declare pertaining to this article.

List of Abbreviation:

AChE	- Acetylcholinesterase
AD	- Alzheimer Disease
APOE	- Apolipoprotein E
A β	- Amyloid beta
BChE	- Butyryl Cholinesterase
MDA	- Malondialdehyde
MPTP	- 1- methyle-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6 tetrahydropyridine
nAChRs	- Nicotinic acetylcholine receptors
NGF	- Nerve Development Factor
NMB	- Nucleus basalis of Meynert
PD	- Parkinsonism Disease

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